

The Role of the Gut Microbiome in Diabetes: Physiological Implications and Therapeutic Potential. A Narrative Review

Rawaa Sahib Abdulhasan ✉

*Nasiriyah Education Department, College of Science, Biology,
Tunisia Preparatory School for Girls, Tunisia*

Abstract

The gut microbiome plays a crucial role in the regulation of metabolic processes, and its dysbiosis has been increasingly implicated in the pathogenesis of diabetes. This narrative review explores the physiological implications of the gut microbiome in diabetes management and its potential as a therapeutic target. We summarize recent findings on how gut microbial composition influences insulin sensitivity, glucose metabolism, and inflammation. Additionally, we discuss the mechanisms through which gut microbiota affect metabolic health, including short-chain fatty acid production and modulation of the immune response. The review also highlights emerging therapeutic strategies, such as probiotics, prebiotics, and dietary interventions, aimed at restoring gut microbiome balance to improve diabetic outcomes. By integrating current research, this review underscores the importance of the gut microbiome in diabetes and its potential to inform innovative treatment approaches.

Keywords: *Gut microbiome, Diabetes, Insulin sensitivity, Dysbiosis, Therapeutic strategies, Short-chain fatty acids.*

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Introduction to Diabetes and the Gut Microbiome

The human body is home to trillions of microbes, mainly bacteria, which not only colonize parts of the body's own tissue but also produce thousands of beneficial molecules for the body. Changes in the healthy human gut microbial community can contribute to changes in metabolic processes and thus be involved in the pathophysiology of various diseases. Diabetes mellitus is a major cause of mortality worldwide due to its association with a higher risk of various complications, including cardiovascular disease, kidney damage, blindness, and peripheral neuropathy. Diabetes affects one in 11 adults and millions of people worldwide would develop diabetes by 2045 (Singer-Englar, Barlow, & Mathur, 2019).

While several pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions exist for the management of diabetes, in many cases, diabetes treatment may still be challenging. Given the potential of the gut microbiota in the modulation of host metabolic processes, it is not surprising that the gut as a target is becoming more popular. Indeed, the gut may be one of the crucial targets for potential, low-risk therapeutic interventions in the prevention and treatment of diabetes mellitus. The current review aims to provide readers with a global vision of the interplay between the gut microbiome and diabetes. We set out to convey an understanding of the gut microbiome and the various roles of the gut microbiome in

the physiology and pathophysiology of diabetes (Vallianou, Stratigou, & Tsagarakis, 2018; Barlow, Yu, & Mathur, 2015).

Understanding the Gut Microbiome

The gut microbiome is a term used to define an extremely complex ecosystem, involving trillions of microorganisms that reside in the gastrointestinal tract of herbivorous and carnivorous species, including humans. The human gut microbiome is a result of exposure to the environment combined with host genetic and dietary factors. Microbiome diversity, the number of microbial species present, and the abundance of each species ensemble are vital to the maintenance of health. The composition of the gut microbiome can be determined; however, at the outset, gut microbiome studies employed the manual identification of some microbial species by culturing in the laboratory, implicating inadequate databases (Yen, & Johnson, 2021).

Advances in biotechnology and laboratory technology, combined with increased computational power, have amplified our understanding of the capabilities and geographical locations of microorganisms in the human body. Interactions between gut microbes and the host, both direct and indirect, maintain a continuous mutual relationship of benefits, including the production and absorption of anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetes signaling molecules. The gut microbiome is the central organ that controls nutrient trafficking into the human body, and food ingestion modulates its composition, particularly the proportion of fiber intake; hence, the composition of the gut microbiome forms a combined representation of food diversity and lifestyle (Liu, et al., 2022; Dave, et al., 2012).

Structure and Composition

The gut microbiome is mainly composed of bacteria, but a range of bacterial, fungal, and viral species reside within the human gut. The species composition of this microscopic ecosystem largely depends on multiple host and environmental factors, such as genetic background, early colonization, breastfeeding, age, presence or history of comorbidities, diet, and a range of physiologic and lifestyle factors. Studies have revealed that the gut microbiome is highly diverse, with most of the multiple thousands of microbial species estimated to live in the human gut set to be described. This cataloging of species is central to the functional understanding of the gut microbiome. Notwithstanding, some phyla predominate in the gut ecosystem within and across individuals. The analysis of the gut microbiota across different subjects shows how human gut species are multiply organized. The microbe distribution in the human population can be used to assess which species are consistently associated with health and which ones are linked to specific diseases (Panda, Guarner, & Manichanh, 2014).

Starting from the information about the structure and composition of the gut microbiota, the functions of the host-microbiota interplay have been inferred, amassing more than 55,000 publications in the last 10 years. Different microbial phyla in the human gut are associated with different functions, or meta-phenotypes. The most widely acknowledged taxonomy of the human gut microbiota includes three main enterotype clusters associated with different levels of *Prevotella*, *Bacteroides*, or *Ruminococcus*. Within these clusters, up to 40% inter-individual diversity has been documented. Thus, multiple species characterize each enterotype, with a core of five species shared among clusters, which the gut microbiota of any given healthy host predominantly relies on. This small, albeit stable and recurrent, subset of microbial species is the so-called core microbiota. Dysbiosis has also been recognized as a characteristic of several health conditions. For both obesity and type 2 diabetes, such dysbiosis includes a drop in some beneficial species, such as butyrate-producing *Bacteroides* and *Akkermansia*, and an immoderate growth of *Alistipes* and *Bacteroides vulgatus*, which are both typical of the gut microbiota of individuals with metabolic diseases. It is, however, the bottom line of the 'many for one' structure-function principle which I anticipate will be the one that we shall need to get to. If the composition of our gut microbiota

is so diverse, diaspore-driven and haphazard that its ecological rules are practically impossible to define, what are the chances that some stable patterns can be attributed to its diversity? And why should we, scientists, be interested in trying to untangle such a giant mess (Blaut, 2018).

According to the extensive literature review carried out here, I explore the possibility that the variety of species populating the human ecosystem is less important per se than the integrated work that some species jointly carry out. Focusing on butyrate production, a case is made for further advanced measurements of this short-chain fatty acid in relation to the gut ecosystem. Finally, I propose that if we have to address any question about the plasticity of the gut microbiota and its implications, it is not 'how much', but 'how many for one' instead (Zhu, et al., 2014).

Functions and Interactions

The multitude of functions attributable to the gut microbiome is indicative of the vastness of evolutionary time and energy that have gone into the development of bacterial metabolisms, which have a meaningful impact on human physiology. The metabolic functions of the gut microbiome assist host physiology by directly contributing to digestive and metabolic functions and the modulation of other interactions within the gut ecosystem. Gut microbes can also modulate host gene expression, secrete factors that signal through host and other microbial receptors, replicate or quench host processes, or are recognized as antigens or pathogens by the host. These pathways interact closely with host signaling pathways. Signal transduction systems in mammals and bacteria, especially G protein-coupled receptors, are similar enough to be readily activated by many of the same signaling molecules in both host and microbe (Frank, Wawro, & Pischon, 2021).

Gut bacteria ferment virtually all substrates that reach the colon to produce numerous compounds, including short-chain fatty acids. Among other contributions to host metabolism, short-chain fatty acids have clear effects on host nutrient metabolism, adipogenesis, and perhaps even host reward pathways. Proteomics through biological time and sequencing has shown that the number of genes in our human ecosystem encoding pathways for every category of life is far too numerous to calculate. There is, however, increasing evidence that it is the diversity of the metagenome that confers functionality. Over 150 human and mouse population-based studies have documented various functional shifts in gut ecosystems, extraordinarily some of which produce the same functional outcomes despite different specific phylogenetic shifts. In interactions with the host, the gut ability of the microbiome to shape inflammation is significant and is able to modulate both inflammation and autoimmunity. Importantly, the net inflammatory effect of changes in the microbiome can become dominant in distal tissues and is usually independent of the particulars of the mushroom. The gut-brain axis in general and the potential mental health implications of dysbiosis in the spectrum of systemic diseases are emerging. Among diseases, the metabolic effect is usually diabetes (Akimbekov, Razzaque, & Lyanova, 2020; Ross, et al., 2024).

Diabetes: Types, Causes, and Complications

Diabetes refers to a group of metabolic diseases and endocrine disorders in which a person has high blood sugar, either due to inadequate insulin production, a lack of insulin action, or both. The three primary types of diabetes are classified as Type 1, Type 2, and gestational diabetes. Type 1 diabetes occurs when the pancreas fails to produce insulin and typically develops in childhood. Type 1 diabetes is considered an autoimmune disease; genetic predispositions may be involved in its development, and an environmental trigger is thought to interact with the immune system and lead to an autoimmune response. Type 2 diabetes, resulting from the pancreas failing to produce enough insulin and the body's cells not responding properly to insulin, is associated with a number of risk factors, including a family history of the disease, being overweight or obese, physical inactivity, and race or ethnicity. Gestational

diabetes occurs during pregnancy when the placenta produces hormones that cause a buildup of glucose in the blood (Kumar, et al., 2020; Cole, & Florez, 2020).

Diabetes can lead to various health complications, including cardiovascular disease, peripheral artery disease, hearing impairment, and neuropathy. Commonly, diabetes is related to long-term damage, dysfunction, and failure of several organs, particularly the eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, and blood vessels; the eyes, kidneys, nerves, and feet are the most commonly affected areas. Diabetes can manifest in an array of symptoms, including excessive thirst and hunger, frequent urination, weight loss, fatigue, vision problems, swelling or numbness in the feet, slow wound healing, skin infections, and even sudden blurry vision, which can be a sign of high blood sugar. Unfortunately, diabetes is incurable. Instead, both prevention and management require learning to control the condition, typically through a combination of proper nutrition, physical activity, weight management, medication, self-monitoring, and occasionally, surgery. Given its multifaceted nature, diabetes management also requires addressing and monitoring various other health concerns, such as high blood pressure or high cholesterol. Globally, diabetes is increasingly common; in 2021, an estimated 10% of the American population had diabetes. Between 2020 and 2021, the number of Americans affected by the disease increased from 29.1 to 34.2 million (Cole, & Florez, 2020; Mauricio, Alonso, & Gratacòs, 2020).

Gut Microbiome Dysbiosis in Diabetes

Mounting evidence supports a role for the gut microbiome in many chronic diseases, including type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes, and diabetes-associated complications. Dysbiosis, or disruption of the gut microbiome, is common in individuals with diabetes, characterized by reduced microbial diversity and alteration of community composition and metabolism. This dysbiosis can contribute to the progression from insulin resistance to type 2 diabetes and the development of micro- and macrovascular complications. Although a cyclical relationship likely exists, evidence from diet-controlled intervention studies in humans and rodent models of diabetes demonstrates that changes in the gut microbiome can directly influence disease pathobiology. However, there is a significant need for additional studies in humans that link baseline dysbiosis to diabetes and translate this into a targeted intervention to restore a healthy microbiome that can prevent the disease (Hamjane, et al., 2024).

Dysbiosis indicates an abnormal state and defines the loss of resilience of the gut microbiome to endure and rapidly recover from environmental changes. The effects of dysbiosis are widespread. In addition to altering the production of microbe-dependent nutrient metabolites, the process of dysbiosis also drives inflammation and epithelial dysfunction, undermines early-life immune competence, and is a key factor in the development of non-communicable diseases. Dysbiosis, therefore, makes an individual more sensitive to additional environmental stress and less capable of drawing on the support of microbial members actively competing against each other. In the current review, we focus on how an individual's gut microbiome can be shaped by external forces and factors, and how some changes, in turn, shape the individual's susceptibility to diabetes (Ojo, et al., 2020; Lau, Vaziri, & Natarajan, 2021).

Mechanisms of Gut Microbiome Influence on Diabetes Development

The mechanisms through which the gut microbiota may influence the development of diabetes are still not totally understood. The prokaryotic microbes in the mammalian intestine ferment indigestible dietary components, endogenous intestinal mucus, and sloughed epithelial cells to produce copious amounts of short-chain fatty acids, which can be absorbed and utilized by the host. These so-called microbial metabolites produced in the intestinal lumen can modulate host metabolism and inflammation. One

putative mechanism through which dysbiosis might influence diabetes is by altering host metabolism and systemic inflammation through the production or degradation of microbial metabolites (Li, et al., 2020).

The number of bacteria in the human gastrointestinal tract, an estimated 10^{14} , exceeds the number of eukaryotic cells in the human body. The human microbiome consists of over one thousand different species and trillions of individual cells with different metabolic profiles. Accumulating evidence suggests that the composition of the gut microbiota and its functional metabolites are associated with the regulation of glucose, lipid, and energy metabolism. Beneficial bacterial strains are generally involved in the regulation of glucose and lipid metabolism. Many specific components encoded by genetic makeup and metabolites of gut bacteria are involved in metabolic regulation and the adaptation of very low-calorie diet-induced glucose homeostasis. But growing evidence has suggested that the bacteria and their metabolites can work in combination to maintain the primary fermenters and the subsequent consumers of fermentation products in mutualistic relationships. This makes the potential of a single metabolic product depending on the acetate production rate difficult to assess (Zhou, Xiong, & Wang, 2020; Zhang, et al., 2021).

Inflammation and Immune Response

Inflammation and immune response: The initiation of inflammation and the immune system have been consistently linked to the etiology of diabetes in both experimental animals and humans. The gut microbiome, together with the gut-liver axis, can shape host susceptibility to developing systemic inflammation. Dysbiosis has been associated with increased pro-inflammatory circulating cytokine levels such as IL-6, IFN γ , and IL-17, thus modulating insulin sensitivity and promoting the development of metabolic disease. IL-6, involved in the hepatic acute phase response, reduces insulin signal transduction by promoting serine phosphorylation of the insulin receptor substrate-1 (IRS-1), resulting in insulin resistance. IL-6 receptor blocking could normalize insulin action and glucose tolerance in rodents. In human studies, increased levels of IL-6, IFN γ , and leptin were associated with the development of type 2 diabetes. TNF α and interferon gamma may induce insulin resistance in different tissues (Rodrigues, et al., 2022).

The gut microbiome and the immune system: The gut microbiome is involved in both systemic and mucosal immune responses. The gut mucosa harbors effector and regulatory T helper cells which secrete pro-inflammatory or anti-inflammatory cytokines and have been shown to be influenced by dietary components and the gut microbiome. Conversely, intestinally conditioned immune cells shape the composition of the gut microbiome. For example, individuals with higher mucosa-associated macrophages and higher concentrations of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α , IFN- γ , and IL-12, were found to have higher levels of *Bacteroides plebeius*, which ameliorated the pro-inflammatory environment by converting dietary flavonoids into the anti-inflammatory isoxanthohumol. Increased prevalence of mucosa-associated effector T cells secreting higher levels of IL-17 has been related to certain conditions. Increased levels of *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Roseburia intestinalis*, *Clostridium* spp., and *Akkermansia muciniphila* are reported in individuals with higher Th2 regulatory T cells. In vivo studies have shown the transfer of lymphocytes from mice fed a polyunsaturated fatty acid-rich diet, which enriched *Lactobacilli*, into germ-free syngeneic counterparts results in the increase of regulatory T cells in the cecal mucosa of the latter. Likewise, the gut microbiome can promote inflammation and metabolic disease including diabetes, as observed in a human study with the simultaneous reduction of insulin sensitivity and mucosal regulatory T cells, and the increase of mucosal effector Th17 cells in diabetic patients with increased abundance of *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Akkermansia muciniphila*, and *Collinsella* (Forrester, Kuffova, & Delibegovic, 2020; Rohm, et al., 2022).

Metabolic Regulation

The combined metabolic capacity of the microbiota, both in the gut and in the systemic circulation, is substantial, with gut microbes closely intertwined with host metabolism via various pathways. The most

well-studied pathways are those of glucose and lipid metabolism. Microorganisms degrade indigestible dietary carbohydrates and endogenous mucus to produce short-chain fatty acids, which are later converted to acetyl-CoA to feed into all host metabolic pathways. An increase in the production of short-chain fatty acids (especially butyrate) has been associated with higher insulin sensitivity, and their intake has also been shown to improve glucose homeostasis and energy expenditure in both mice and humans. Glycolysis in microbes outcompetes that in colonic epithelial cells, signaling that the production of microbial short-chain fatty acids might precede other effects due to a change in metabolic pathway. Reductions in glucose metabolism (via low butyrate concentration) could also result in a decrease in overall ATP levels (due to fewer potential substrates feeding into the tricarboxylic acid cycle), which might lead to a depletion of cellular energy. Microbes are thus able to modulate both the supply of energy and the release of hormones to regulate its use (Tramunt, et al., 2020).

Furthermore, these observations adequately explain the reciprocal interactions that exist between the gut microbiome and diet, as well as the additional difficulties related to whether certain functions are beneficial or harmful when assessing microbial features. An imbalance of these metabolic processes has indeed been observed in those with dysbiosis, including alterations in amino acid and carbohydrate metabolism. The synthesis and excretion of bile acids, as well as bile acid transformations, might also be disturbed in dysbiosis. Bile acids have roles in endocrine pathways influencing glucose metabolism, signaling through the farnesoid X receptor, and also act as antimicrobial compounds. The gut microbes can also provide various endocrine or energy-relevant hormones, including glucagon-like peptides, peptide YY, and short-chain fatty acids. The latter impact lipid metabolism and also act as incretins. Incretins are hormones that are normally produced in the gut and released by meals, putting them at the interface of metabolism and microbiome. Low levels of butyrate (or propionate) in conjunction with high levels of other short-chain fatty acids serve to increase the levels of the anorexigenic hormones, peptide YY, and glucagon-like peptide 1, as well as reducing ghrelin (Navarro, 2020).

In animal models, loss of FFA3 regulates vagal afferent nerve activity and markers of appetite and metabolism. The manipulation of the gut microbiome provides another “window,” potentially through dietary prebiotic substrates or dietary fibers, which reduce the numbers of Proteobacterial populations. In return, through their metabolic activity, the microbiome can then signal back to the host’s tissue the beneficial effects, such as improving glucometabolic function. The host-microbiota metabolism-immunity axis is also likely to be involved in these interconnections. An acute inflammatory response during endotoxin administration creates insulin resistance and especially follows the conservation of energy, but not the activity of energy consumption mechanisms. Chronic resistant inflammation and energy imbalance exacerbate the risk of developing T2D, CVD, NAFLD/NASH, and ASCVD. Finally, it is fairly clear how intertwined energy conservation is with the microbiome, both in our evolutionary path and restoration of “normal” metabolism (Dilworth, Facey, & Omoruyi, 2021).

Clinical Studies and Evidence

In the last few years, a number of clinical studies have been conducted to assess the impact of the gut microbiome on diabetes. Disease incidence has been linked to specific taxa or changes in the diversity and composition of the microbiome. Ideally, these findings would serve as a more sensitive method of predicting disease status compared to traditional methods, as they represent alterations that occur very early in the disease pathophysiology. Most prospective studies have indeed demonstrated an association between the microbiome and incident diabetes. There is a large body of evidence from observational studies based on descriptive changes in the microbiome over the course of diabetes and T2D. The relationships of T2D with obesity, metabolic syndrome, and insulin resistance have been reported, but it is not immediately clear whether the relationship is caused by different microbiome compositions or vice versa (Navaneethan, et al., 2021).

Among many studies, mechanisms have been the topic of interest in diet and drug intervention trials. Successful findings in the studies also have therapeutic relevance since they show that glycemic control can be modulated through nutritional intervention. Certain aspects of this evidence may be interesting for diabetologists and metabolic researchers as well as for health care workers who want to use this dietary aspect in clinical care. In general, the potential beneficial involvement of the microbiome metabolites in T2D must be supported, and it must also be ascertained that the recovery is mainly for microbiota-dependent health. The main limitation of most microbiota studies is the fact that many results are from mostly observational, poorly designed clinical studies. There is also a disadvantage that this result may be biased by not adjusting for underlying confounding factors such as nutritional status and genetic variations in host susceptibility. In summary, there is still no definitive formula to recommend the type, amount, and frequency of food intake, as well as information about how the individual food matrix and the functional structures in it work to establish or maintain a balanced microbiome. Such knowledge is important for diabetologists in order to exploit their therapeutic potential. What does all this evidence currently mean for physicians? The information about the microbiome composition should provide a clearer view and information regarding the treatment and therapy approach in patients with diabetes who are often diagnosed (Tan, et al., 2020; Pagidipati, et al., 2023).

Therapeutic Approaches Targeting the Gut Microbiome in Diabetes

The manipulation of the gut microbiome emerges as a promising target to improve diabetes pathophysiology. This section takes an in-depth view of the various therapeutic strategies that aim to alter the gut ecosystem in the interests of restoring eubiosis and improving metabolic disease outcomes. These therapeutic targets include dietary interventions to improve the quality of the gut microbiome and modifications in the gut microbiome components, including the use of probiotics, prebiotics, and fecal microbiota transplantation (Liu, et al., 2022).

The modulation of the gut microbiome has been considered a potentially new strategy for diabetes prevention and treatment. Importantly, many of these compounds and strategies offer the potential to act locally in the gut to alter gut microorganisms favorable for reducing diabetes risk or ameliorating diabetes complications. There are several strategies for the modulation of the intestinal microbiome, which include modulating disease-related microorganisms, restoring the balance between the microbiome, and making use of beneficial microbial species. Several alternative strategies have emerged in this area, which can be grouped by their underlying exponents: one proposes the use of probiotics and prebiotics to promote dialogue between the gut microbiota and the host and induce gastrointestinal remodeling, and the other advocates for interventions such as fecal microbiota transplantation and phytotherapies with pre-tailored compounds capable of promoting corrective action in the gut ecosystem (Adeshirlarijaney, & Gewirtz, 2020; Huda, Kim, & Bennett, 2021; Schupack, et al., 2022).

Probiotics and Prebiotics

Ecologically, probiotics are defined as live microorganisms that, when adequately administered, confer health benefits on the host. Many healthy individuals take probiotics daily seeking benefits for all kinds of ailments, among them metabolic disease. Importantly, several clinical trials and meta-analyses have shown that certain species present an antidiabetic action on the diabetic population. In combination, prebiotics are defined as non-digestible food components that stimulate the growth and/or activity of beneficial microbes, inducing a positive ecological benefit. Interestingly, an enzyme from *Bifidobacterium* could produce fructooligosaccharides by exoinulinase or fructosyltransferase activity. This and other data produced a revival of the prebiotic idea. Some dietary fibers have the same effect as prebiotic agents. Prebiotics are selectively fermented ingredients that allow specific changes, both in the composition and/or activity in the gastrointestinal microflora that confer benefits upon host well-being and health.

This is particularly aimed at preventing and treating select gastrointestinal disorders, rather than generally promoting health (Cunningham, et al., 2021).

Various commercial names and formulations of the above interventions are available on the consumer market, and it has become evident that specific probiotic combinations exert unique metabolic activity in different groups of people. Microbiome studies confirm that probiotic ingestion can have long-lasting effects on the host metabolic status. A short high-probiotic supplementation period can positively alter the composition of the fecal microbiome; this observable alteration is further increased by periodical, lower-dose supplementation. Importantly, a probiotic supplement that has been found to reduce HbA1c and to improve fasting insulin in humans was also shown to exert a positive glycemic effect in one subgroup of prediabetics. Organic acids produced by the ingested probiotic were found in the fecal samples of the supplementing study subjects, indicating a possible mechanism for the observed positive metabolic effects (Swanson, et al., 2020; Marco, et al., 2021).

Dietary Interventions

Currently, strategies to manipulate the microbial community target factors related to the diet to improve glycaemia and increase the diversity and function of the microbiome, assessed by gut microbiome-metabolic pathways and host-microbial interactions. This notion implies that dietary change would lead to a shift in the microbial composition and function and subsequently improve gut and metabolic dysbiosis. Essential in translating dietary habits to microbiome composition and function is the nutr microbiome, personalized nutrition strategies based on the individual microbiome composition and related gene functions, and metabolic insufficiency besides general metabolic considerations. Studies reporting dietary habits of healthy or non-diabetic individuals showed that favoring a varied intake of foods, legumes, unprocessed cereals, nuts, various fruits, wild vegetables, lake and sea fish, milk, and derived fermented products, together with reduced intake of red or processed meat, high processed food or drinks of any kind, and animal fat. This description seems to fit with some diet patterns already reported to be associated with particular microbiota composition and/or function and a reduced risk of developing diabetes or specific diabetes-related disorders, such as the Mediterranean diet or plant-based diets. Diet-related components found to be promising for a healthy gut microbiota influence are the intake of prebiotics and probiotics, together with avoiding inappropriate use of antibiotics. Recently, personalized recommendations also suggest decreasing saturated fat intake, food sources of L-carnitine and choline, as well as higher fiber intake, which are all closely linked to a healthy microbiome (Toi, et al., 2020). Targeting these strategies might first change the individuals' gut microbiome composition and function, providing evidence of an important interaction in between, and secondly ameliorate complications connected with an inappropriate microbial community setting. Results from some randomized controlled trials demonstrated that dietary changes acceptable for the individuals can improve these aspects. Several studies report an effect of dietary changes on perceived symptoms, among which alterations in stool consistency and frequency report improved levels. Besides these parameters, also possible changes in other factors, more related to microbiome composition and function, are analyzed including stool pH and specific bacterial counts like Clostridium groups or specific microorganisms like methanogens, which can contribute to flatulence (Vlachos, Malisova, & Lindberg, 2020). Additionally, changes in metabolites have also been analyzed, such as short-chain fatty acids and low abundance metabolites like oxalates. Individual case studies have associated other gut score markers along with diabetes-associated symptoms. These findings support the idea of personalized nutrition, although they need to be confirmed in larger studies. Enforcement modalities and personalized consultations can help more strictly apply these dietary regulations to ameliorate their efficacy in reaching stool microbiota and causative metabolic community height, together with reducing the bacterial homeostasis-altering phenomena. This is a delicate aspect in providing personalized nutrition and should be implemented in future studies together with psychological and social science tools, providing new nutrition counseling strategies in order to overcome this limit (Che, et al., 2021).

Fecal Microbiota Transplantation

Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) is an emerging therapeutic strategy for the restoration of a healthy gut microbiome in the setting of type 2 diabetes and diabetes-associated comorbidities. The procedure consists of the transfer of stool from a healthy donor into a patient; its main aim is to replete the performance of an optimal and eubiotic ecosystem within the patient's large bowel. At present, results from uncontrolled case series and open-label studies have shown that FMT can beneficially modulate human glycemic control and might also improve the metabolic profile of diabetic individuals. At the experimental level, FMT exerted meaningful metabolic beneficial effects in murine models, as has been reported to increase insulin sensitivity, modify glucose levels, and improve lipid metabolism. The overall action of FMT might depend on multiple factors, and a direct causal role of the gut microbiome in the ultimate modulation of glycemic control by FMT has been claimed (Porcari, et al., 2023).

Notwithstanding initial experimental and clinical successes, there are several challenges that are emerging in the current application of FMT. These challenges range from donor selection to safety, regulatory, and ethical responsibilities. In particular, there are risks for the transmission of infectious diseases, pathobionts, resistance genes, and harmful metabolic traits. Despite its compelling therapeutic potential, large-scale evidence in many areas of medicine and surgery will be required before it can be stipulated in the latest international guidelines. Particularly, the ultimate acknowledgment of this practice in clinical diabetology may only come from the results of large-scale multicenter, double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized clinical trials with extensive follow-ups. In addition, it is still unknown whether the beneficial effects of the first FMT administration(s) can be maintained over time, even after interruptions, and whether other sequential transfers will result in further therapeutic advantages. In this context, the development of more rational strategies, other than the standard FMT procedures in open capsules or nasojejunal tubes, might change the landscape of the available therapies. Therefore, there is growing interest and a broad field of research focusing on therapies exploiting the beneficial part of the gut microbiome or its pharmacological derivatives for the treatment of diabetes being developed (Cheng, & Fischer, 2023; Hanssen, de Vos, & Nieuwdorp, 2021).

Future Directions and Research Challenges

One key point is that evidence is mandatory to allow the microbiome changes to be harnessed for therapeutic interventions and to adopt a precision medicine approach to treat diabetic subjects, since the potential of the microbiome is not exclusively positive but can also have harmful implications for the host. Although there is growing interest in the role of gut-brain communication in association with diabetes, very few studies have been conducted in this area. It is unclear whether the gut-brain link is fundamental to the personalized medicine field, but its study is mandatory and could be potentially relevant. The role played by the gut microbiota in controlling diabetes and its pathological outcomes is still an area that requires further investigation. Many trials have been conducted or are ongoing, although they are still in the recruitment phase. Many questions remain unanswered and are therefore a stimulus for future research (Çöltekin, et al., 2020).

Another relevant idea is represented by the fact that further studies including larger sample sizes could confirm the conclusions drawn. Only a few promising findings have been suggested, and these recommendations state that further longitudinal studies are encouraged to investigate the association between modifications in the gut microbiome and clinical outcomes. In fact, the gut microbiome is extremely heterogeneous among individuals with diabetes and is determined by the external and internal individual stimuli and pressure. In this field, the value of including multi-omics techniques measuring variations in the genomic, proteomic, and metabolomic pathways carried out by the microbiome appears to be under-explored. It is extremely important to manage the ethical aspects of performing microbiome

research, especially for the development of a future personalized or precision intervention. The theory is still at an early stage: most of the research is dedicated to understanding single gut microbial changes, although gut microbiome research is, by itself, a complex and interdisciplinary subject, including but not limited to diet, genetics, metabolomics, biochemistry, and immunology. Certainly, the achievement of a consensus concerning the optimal analytical software and pipeline to perform high-quality microbiome research is mandatory. Therefore, the main aspect of future research lies in studying the field considering collaboration between multiple disciplines and the possibility to include a larger and more diverse cohort of the population using standardized measurements and intervention procedures. The thesis is to improve the relevance of microbiome profiling not only on outcomes but also in clinical practice. However, the large variability in response to lifestyle and therapeutic interventions should constitute an interesting field for the application of microbiome techniques. Finally, various options to modulate the gut microbiome and communications at the base of the gut-brain axis are the major option to act in the personalized treatment approach (Singh, & Behal, 2020; Yang, Luo, & Huang, 2020).

Conclusion and Implications for Diabetes Management

Aside from the role of the gut microbiome in the management of metabolic comorbidities, a great deal has yet to be learned about the impact of different pathological states of the human gut ecosystem on systemic as well as whole-body metabolism. Potential therapeutic intervention in the management of dysbiosis at the level of the individual will depend upon such insights. It is clear, however, that abnormal presumed deleterious effects on islet function and insulin turnover are closely associated with the gut ecosystem's metabolic potential. The anatomy and physiology of the human gut make the trillions of microorganisms living within it likely targets for improved therapeutic regimens. It is expected that prevailing gastromicrobial health will vary greatly from one individual to another and that the effects of microbial therapy will be most pronounced in the symptomatic patient. The current weight of opinion suggests that gastromicrobial pathology is best considered from a population care perspective. Epigenetic and aging research may eventually contribute to the discovery and implementation of gastromicrobial therapies to promote long-term health. Changes in diet and environmental exposures are among the factors likely to contribute to this field. It has become increasingly clear that regulatory control of whole-body energy balance, including endocrine function, is influenced heavily by the gut microbiome, an ever-changing community of over 100 trillion organisms. Disruption in the homeostatic equilibrium between humans and their microbial inhabitants has been implicated in the pathogenesis of diabetes, in particular type 2 diabetes. Animal studies and human intervention trials confirm the significant benefits to health inherent in the correction of gut dysbiosis, offering exciting possibilities for the emergence of microbiome-based therapies in diabetes practice. However, characterization and manipulation of the gut microbiome will be complex at the level of the individual. Moreover, results from human studies lack consistency, with heterogeneity in the methodologies used to investigate gut microbes. Collaboration between those working in the fields of microbiology, endocrinology, and public health will be critical in exploring the possibilities. Given the potential for microbiome-based therapies, these collaborations are imperative and should continue to feature prominently in diabetes research with a view to translating results into tangible benefits for patients in due course. It may very well be prudent, therefore, to integrate therapies utilizing the gut microbiome into future clinical therapies for diabetes and other metabolic conditions. Further work is needed to uncover these mechanisms affecting the microbiota, which may yet provide additional targets for potential therapeutic interventions.

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